

Galaxy Formation & Evolution in the Era of the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope

2020 October 5

10:00 - 12:00	Session 1: Introductions	
10:00 - 10:15	1a Welcome & Introduction	
10:15 - 10:45	1b Roeland van der Marel (STScI):	The Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope
10:45 - 11:15	1c Jen Lotz (Gemini Obs.):	Overview of Galaxy Formation
11:15 - 11:45	1d Dara Norman (NOIRLab):	Advancing Inclusion Through Access
11:45 - 12:00	1e Q&A/Discussion	
12:00 - 12:30	Break	
12:30 - 14:00	Session 2: Connecting the Near-Field and Deep Field View of Galaxy Formation	Chair: Preethi Nair (U. Alabama)
12:30 - 13:00	2a Invited Talk: James Bullock (UCI)	Invited Talk
13:00 - 13:15	2b Ben Williams (UW)	Surveying Nearby Galaxies with Roman
13:15 - 13:30	2c Kristen McQuinn (Rutgers)	The Roman Space Telescope: A Pathway to Measuring Accurate Distances to Every Galaxy in the Nearby Universe
13:30 - 13:45	2d Raja GuhaThakurta (UCSC)	Three Roman Telescope Science Cases for Local Volume Galaxies
13:45 - 14:00	2e Sarah Pearson (Flatiron Inst.)	Stellar Streams from Globular Clusters in the Local Universe
14:00 - 15:00	Posters	
15:00 - 16:00	Science Writers Workshop	Closed to Participants but recording will be available later

2020 October 6

10:00 - 11:30	Session 3: High-Redshift Galaxies	Chair: Harry Ferguson (STSCI)
10:00 - 10:30	3a Invited Talk: Rebecca Bowler (Univ. of Oxford)	Invited Talk
10:30 - 10:45	3b Micaela Bagley (Univ. of Texas)	Going deep with Roman: the $z > 9$ UV luminosity function
10:45 - 11:00	3c Isak Wold (NASA/GSFC)	Lya Emitters at Cosmic Dawn with a Deep Roman Grism Survey
11:00 - 11:15	3d Anton Koekemoer (STScI)	Ultra Deep Field Science with the Roman Space Telescope
11:15 - 11:30	3e Gourav Khullar (Univ of Chicago)	The Brightest Galaxy in the $z > 5$ Universe: Observing Distant Lensed Galaxies with RST
11:30 - 12:00	3f James Rhoads (NASA/GSFC)	SIT Talk
12:00 - 12:30	Break	
12:30 - 14:00	Session 4: AGN and Black Holes	Chair: Jenny Greene (Princeton)
12:30 - 13:00	4a Invited Talk: Jonelle Walsh (Texas A&M)	Elucidating the Black Hole - Galaxy Connection
13:00 - 13:15	4b Tyrone Woods (NRCC)	The origin of the most massive, high-redshift quasars
13:15 - 13:30	4c Feige Wang (Univ. of Arizona)	Finding the First Luminous Quasars
13:30 - 13:45	4d Andreea Petric (STScI)	Obscured AGN at the Cosmic Noon
13:45 - 14:00	4e Marie Wingyee Lau (UCR)	Probing Feedback and Quasar/galaxy Evolution with Extremely Red Quasars
14:00 - 15:00	Posters	
15:00 - 16:00	Public Talk	
	Jennifer Wiseman (NASA)	Nancy Grace Roman, the Astronomer
	Julie McEnery (GSFC)	Nancy Grace Roman, the Space Telescope

2020 October 7

10:00 - 11:30	Session 5: Data Science for Astropysics in the Roman Era	Chair: Arianna Cortesi (Observatorio Do Valongo)
10:00 - 10:30	5a Invited Talk: Eric Gawiser (Rutgers)	Astrophysical Data Science in the Roman Era
10:30 - 10:45	5b Sidney Lower (Univ of Florida)	Ground-Truthing SED Fitting Methods in Galaxy Observations
10:45 - 11:00	5c Sankalp Gilda (Univ of Florida)	mirkwood: SED fitting for the twenty first century
11:00 - 11:15	5d Lorenzo Zanisi (Univ of Southampton)	A deep learning approach to quantitatively compare the fine stellar morphology of simulated and real galaxies
11:15 - 11:30	5e Marc Huertas-Company (IAC)	Making Discoveries with Generative Models in the Era of the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope
11:30 - 12:00	5f iPosters & Discussion	
12:00 - 12:30	Break	
12:30 - 14:00	Session 6: Relating the Dark Matter Density Field to Galaxy Properties	Chair: Lorenzo Zanisi (Univ. of Southampton)
12:30 - 13:00	6a Invited Talk: Casey Papovich (Texas A&M)	Invited talk
13:00 - 13:15	6b Mariko Kubo (Ehime Univ)	Protocluster survey/characterization with NGRST
13:15 - 13:30	6c Song Huang (Princeton)	Connecting the Bright and Dark Sides of Massive Galaxies in the Universe
13:30 - 13:45	6d Jenna Samuel (UCD)	Predictions for satellite galaxy distributions around Milky Way analogs with NGRST
13:45 - 14:00	6e Scott Chapman (UBC)	Massive Galaxy Protoclusters in the Early Universe uncovered by the South Pole Telescope
14:00 - 15:00	Posters	

2020 October 8

10:00 - 11:30	Session 7: Dust & Star-Formation in Galaxies	Chair: Vivian U (UCI)
10:00 - 10:30	7a Invited Talk: Daniela Calzetti (UMass, Amherst)	Dust and Star Formation in Galaxies: Not the Entire Story
10:30 - 10:45	7b Andrew Battisti (ANU)	Sweeping Away the Dust: Understanding the Evolution of Attenuation up to the Peak of Cosmic Star Formation
10:45 - 11:00	7c Claude-Andre Faucher-Giguere (Northwestern)	A new paradigm for the formation of disk galaxies & its implications for star formation variability, galactic winds, & quenching
11:00 - 11:15	7d Hermine Landt (Durham Univ)	Astrochemistry of the Dust Around Supermassive Black Holes in the New Era of Transient Infrared Sky Surveys
11:15 - 11:30	7e Anahita Alavi (IPAC)	Dust attenuation measurement for high-redshift dwarf galaxies
11:30 - 12:00	7f iPosters & Discussion	
12:00 - 12:30	Break	
12:30 - 14:00	Session 8: Challenges for Theory, Modeling, and Synthetic Observations	Chair: Camilla Pacifici (STScI)
12:30 - 13:00	8a Invited Talk: Risa Wechsler (Stanford)	Invited Talk
13:00 - 13:15	8b Nicole Drakos (UCSC)	A Mock Catalog for a Roman Telescope Ultra Deep Field
13:15 - 13:30	8c John Weaver (Cosmic Dawn Center)	The COSMOS2020 Catalog: A stepping stone for the next generation of galaxy surveys
13:30 - 13:45	8d Prerak Garg (Univ of Florida)	Modeling nebular emission in galaxy formation simulations
13:45 - 14:00	8e Aritra Ghosh (Yale)	Studying Morphology & Quenching of Galaxies in the NGRST Era using Interpretable Convolutional Neural Networks
14:00 - 15:00	Posters	

2020 October 9

10:00 - 11:30	Session 9: Synergies with Wavelengths & Facilities	Chair: Andreea Petric (STScI)
10:00 - 10:30	9a Invited Talk: Ranga-Ram Chary (IPAC)	Unsolved issues in Galaxy Evolution at the Epoch of Reionization
10:30 - 10:45	9b Manda Banerji (Univ of Southampton)	Galaxies Science with the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space Time (LSST): The Need for Infra-red Data
10:45 - 11:00	9c Lucia Pozzetti (INAF-Bologna)	Galaxy formation and evolution in the era of Euclid
11:00 - 11:15	9d Lukas Zalesky (IoA)	The Hawaii Twenty Square Degree Survey: Synergy with Next Generation Space Telescopes
11:15 - 11:30	9e Adam Muzzin (York)	Resolving Problems in Galaxy Formation with HST, WFIRST and GIRMOS
11:30 - 12:00	9f Brant Robertson (UCSC)	SIT Talk
12:00 - 12:30	Break	
12:30 - 14:00	Session 10: Galaxy Formation across Decades of Physical Scales	Chair: Takahiro Morishita (STScI)
12:30 - 13:00	10a Invited Talk: Tommaso Treu (UCLA)	Galaxies and Dark Matter
13:00 - 13:15	10b Danilo Marchesini (Tufts)	SMF2020: The Ultimate Wedding-Cake Measurements of the Stellar Mass Functions of Galaxies since $z=6$
13:15 - 13:30	10c Eric Bell (Univ of Michigan)	Small-scale cosmology with satellite galaxies in the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope Era
13:30 - 13:45	10d Katy Rodriguez Wimberly (UCI)	Ultrafaint Dwarf Galaxies: Smallest Scales Quenching & Predictions
13:45 - 14:00	10e Yuanyuan Zhang (Fermilab)	Studying the diffuse light components of galaxies and galaxy clusters using a stacking method
14:00 - 14:15	Concluding Remarks	